

ENERGY IN INTERNATIONAL STANDARDS**Nurullayev Orzikul Ubaevich***Jizpi is a senior teacher of the "Electrical Technology" department.**Phone: +998919431810; orziqulnurullayev63@gmail.com*

Annotation: International standards contribute more and more to the energy sector, helping to improve the safety and efficiency of production, distribution and use of energy by all participants, ensuring quality and reliability, carrying out multifunctional control, as well as reducing waste and environmental impact.

Аннотация: Международные стандарты вносят все больший вклад в энергетический сектор, помогая повышать безопасность и эффективность производства, распределение и использование энергии всеми участниками, обеспечивая качество и надежность, осуществляя многофункциональный контроль, а также сокращение отходов и влияние на окружающую среду [1].

As in many other ranges, international standards have made and will continue to make an increasing contribution to the energy sector, helping to improve the safety and efficiency of energy production, distribution and use by all participants in the economic market, ensuring quality and reliability, making possible multifunctional control, interoperability and mutual communication, as well as reducing waste and the impact on the environment [2]. They contribute to the development of the market and the introduction of energy-efficient technologies and pave the way for the development and use of alternative renewable energy sources [3].

International standards are powerful tool for the dissemination of new technologies and best practices, developing global markets and supporting the

coordination of government policies on energy efficiency and renewable energy on a global scale [4].

Over the past few years, global demand for energy resources has exceeded the volume of new energy supplies to the market, and in the longer term, by definition, it will be impossible to rely on non-renewable energy sources anymore [5]. Until this point is reached, it is now obvious that humanity is facing a problem and to meet the future energy demand in the most balanced way [6]. The role of standards. So, what is necessary in order to make the transition to more sustainable, but at the same time economically acceptable energy solutions, and what role can standards play in this [7]?

Most technologies, including renewable energy, should provide savings and achieve profitability, thanks to large volumes of implementation and a gradual increase in productivity as knowledge about them accumulates [8].

Many energy-efficient technologies and best practices are already highly cost-effective, but additional barriers that include hold them back [9]:

lack of awareness of the potential for savings;

insufficient or fragmentary information on energy efficiency lack of a common system of indicators [10];

insufficient attention to the issues of energy efficiency of systems and processes, As a consequence of these constraining factors, the purchase and operation of energy-consuming equipment is often entirely focused on optimizing the initial costs, rather than the costs over the entire service life [11], which negatively affects its overall efficiency [12].

Many measures need to be taken to overcome these obstacles, and technical as well as management standards underlie most of them. In the case of energy-consuming equipment, the standards make it possible to measure, compare and evaluate on a general basis such an otherwise invisible characteristic as energy efficiency [13]. This is an important step to successfully overcome most of the important obstacles that are difficult to see and learn.

Where common standards are adopted for measuring, defining, comparing, providing information and verifying energy efficiency, they provide equal conditions for all market participants [14].

Thus, where it makes practical sense, it is desirable to introduce harmonized standards. The consistency of these energy efficiency standards helps:

minimize the costs of testing and verifying the energy efficiency of products for increasingly globalized markets of energy-consuming equipment [15];

make it possible to compare energy efficiency on a common basis across a variety of economic and political groups [24];

simplify the implementation of more efficient production;

accelerate the implementation of best practices in policy measures [16].

From other side, it is important that international standards stipulate energy efficiency measures that would correspond to local conditions, so that in cases where the energy efficiency of equipment is sensitive to the prevailing operating temperature of the environment, the standards allow obtaining the correct results for the given area [16].

Technical standards in the field of energy efficiency should not be limited to measurements and determination of energy efficiency parameters [23]. They may include testing tools, certification and labeling tools and could include broader topics related to systems and processes, such as energy management and ways to monitor, identify and verify energy savings achieved through various methods and programs [17].

What international standards offer? Thus, international standards provide [22]: a consistent and clear framework describing technologies and best practices in relevant areas, including, inter alia, terminology, classifications, testing methods, performance indicators (along with forms of presentation of test results and performance levels) and best management experience; modern knowledge formalized by recognized experts in this field and based on

international consensus, which is the result of a balance of interests reflecting technological, economic and public interests in the vast majority of countries of the world [18].

international standards can help support cooperation and coordination of public policy measures in these areas [19];

The development and implementation of these broader standards is a part of the infrastructure that will facilitate the development of more homogeneous and international energy efficiency markets [20]. At the same time, it will help bring closer the day when energy efficiency can be bought and sold as one of the energy services, just as electricity or gas is currently being sold and bought [21].

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